

Free Particle Momentum and Phase Shift as Spatial Manifestations of an Interaction?

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In previous notes, we have argued for the free particle temporal and spatial resolutions: \hbar/E and \hbar/p on the grounds of degeneracies in the Lorentz invariant $A = -Et+px$, i.e. to $+n\hbar/E$ and $x=x_0+n\hbar/p$ yield the same A value. Here n is an integer.

We note that viewing a stationary particle from different frames with various constant $-v$ values is identical to having various interactions accelerate the particle to these v values. In other words, \hbar/p and \hbar/E are consequences of an interaction which changes E and p . Specifically, this manifestation of an interaction appears as a resolution scheme in space (and time).

If one has gradations or intervals in time and space, one may try to assign a probability to these, namely $\exp(-iEt) \exp(ipx)$ (which we discuss). This shows the effects of the interaction on space in a probabilistic manner. Mathematically, however, $\exp(ipx)$ is not the most general solution showing an effect of an interaction in space. $\exp(ipx + i \text{ phase shift})$ is more general. The question then becomes: What kind of interaction would produce a phase shift, if in fact any at all? We consider two examples: 1D reflection-refraction and the Bohm-Aharonov effect.

\hbar/p and \hbar/e Resolutions from Special Relativity

We have argued in a number of previous notes that the free particle quantum resolutions \hbar/E (time) and \hbar/p (space) follow from the Lorentz invariant:

$$A = -Et+px \quad ((1))$$

If $t=t_0 + n\hbar/E$ and $x=x_0+n\hbar/p$, A remains the same. Here n is an integer which creates a gradation set in time and space. These gradations are linked with E and p , but it is these variables which change in an interaction. In fact, p is proportional to an impulse. Thus, one might expect the uncertainty in x,t (due to the resolutions) to have something to do with interactions, which is the case.

Physically, one may apply an interaction to a particle at rest to give it a constant velocity, instead of using the frame (at constant $-v$) in special relativity. The two are equivalent. As a result, \hbar/p and \hbar/E are manifestations of the effects of past interactions.

If one tries to create a sense of probability, one would expect a periodic function to describe the intervals \hbar/p , for example. This, however, cannot describe movement to the left and right, nor does it treat space points x as equivalent if there is no interaction. This leads to the notion of $\exp(ipx)$ or two dimensional dynamic probability.

One may note that $\cos(px)=\cos(-px)$ because this dimension simply establishes the gradations. It is the second dimension which establishes the direction of movement. This is no different than the idea of two dimensions x,t which are needed to establish movement to the right or left, we argue.

The idea of $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ having positive and negative values is necessary because if one creates a sum using p_1, p_2 etc then $\exp(ip_1x) + \exp(ip_2x)$ interfere to create a new

gradation scheme which is fine because one does not have either p_1 or p_2 , but a kind of average, i.e. interference. Thus, interference creates the sense of an unusual interaction which does not create either p_1 only or p_2 only.

Given $\exp(ipx)$, we have argued that it manifests the results of a previous interaction or a series of interactions. One cannot really tell how p was created. Mathematically, however, $\exp(ipx)$ is not the most general solution with modulus 1. One may have:

$$\text{Exp} (ipx + i \text{ phase shift}) \quad ((1))$$

If ipx manifests the results of an interaction (which changes/creates p), the phase shift should also be linked with an interaction for consistency, but apparently is not associated with one which changes p . That begs the question: What kind of interaction is this and why should it physically exist? One does not see this in Newtonian mechanics.

It is known that a probability manifestation in space through sums of $\exp(ipx)$ s and their interferences creates a kind of average interaction. It is also known that $\exp(ipx + i \text{ phase shift})$ can change the resolution pattern produced as well as peak values. This becomes important if one wishes to have continuity in x at a junction- as in the 1D reflection-refraction problem.

Reflection-Refraction

We have argued for the existence of a probability $\exp(ipx)$ in space based on special relativity. This manifests the effects of a momentum changing interaction in terms of probability. We note that if one has a particle with rest mass, m_0 , at $x=0$ at t , then for $-v_1$ and $-v_2$ (constant speed moving frames) one obtains p_1, p_2 , but also x_1' and x_2' . In other words, the x position changes differently. $\exp(ip_1x)$ and $\exp(ip_2x)$ are both 1 at $x=0$. They do not reflect this shift in x_1' and x_2' . $\exp(ipx)$ only serves to show the effect of a momentum changing interaction.

If $\exp(ipx)$ is a kind of probability in space, one should be able to add $\exp(ipx)$ s in an OR probability situation. This leads to interference which creates new resolution and new peak heights if one has different weights for the $\exp(ipx)$ s.

If one has a problem in which there are different Sum over p $a(p)\exp(ipx)$ functions to the right and left of an x_0 point, then one needs to have continuity (function and first derivative) at x_0 . This requires an interference which allows for such continuity. The interference, however, is a manifestation of the interaction, we argue in this note. To be explicit, consider $A=1$ representing an incident photon, $|B|$ a reflected and $|C|$, a refracted. If one tries to write (for $p_2 > p_1$):

$$\exp(ip_1x) + |B| \exp(-ip_1x) = |C| \exp(ip_2x) \quad ((2)) \quad \text{at } x_0=0, \text{ then}$$

$$((2)) \text{ implies that: } 1 + |B| = |C| \quad ((3))$$

$$\text{For the first derivative } d/dx \text{ continuity equation, one would have: } p_1 (1 + |B|) = p_2 |C| \quad ((4))$$

For $p_2 > p_1$ $1 + |B| > |C|$, but this contradicts ((3)). For consistency, one requires B to be negative for $p_2 > p_1$. This may be described by a phase shift as well as $p \rightarrow -p$ for the reflected photon.

This phase shift can be measured by showing interference patterns for the reflected photon with other photons.

The interaction on the incident photon does two things: it changes $p \rightarrow -p$, but also introduces a phase shift of 3.14 i.e. $\exp(i 3.14) = -1$. A change in p is not enough. Thus, phase shifts do exist in nature and are a manifestation of an interaction, we argue. If that is the case, one may try to look for them elsewhere.

The Case of an Interaction Which Does Not Change Momentum

In the 1D reflection-refraction case, it was argued that an interaction can change both p and create a phase shift. In Newtonian mechanics, only p is changed. It is possible for an interaction to simply change p as in the case of special relativistic frames. This begs the question: Why should one not consider an interaction which only introduces a phase shift?

One would not expect this to happen in a vacuum, so one might suggest a potential for which no force acts on a particle moving in one dimension. This is possible in the case of the Lorentz force $q \mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B}$. $\mathbf{B} = \text{grad} \times \mathbf{A}$, so there is a magnetic vector potential and \mathbf{B} field, but no force. It is possible that the particle interacts with \mathbf{B} (or \mathbf{A}), but does not change its p . In such a case, one would expect to see a phase shift which manifests this interaction. If one allows a charged particle which passes through such a \mathbf{B} field (or \mathbf{A}) to interfere with one which does not, they have different interaction profiles in space, i.e. one is phase shifted and this leads to an interference as is well-known (i.e. the Bohm-Aharonov case).

Conclusion

In conclusion, we consider $\exp(ipx)$, linked to the spatial resolution, as being the manifestation of an interaction which changes p . Mathematically, $\exp(ipx + i \text{ phase shift})$ is a more general dynamic probability, but that does not mean it exists in nature. We argue, however, that interactions can change both p and introduce a phase shift in some cases. We cite the interaction on an incident photon reflecting at an n_1 - n_2 index of refraction junction in 1D as an example. It is not enough for p to change to $-p$, a 3.14 phase shift must also occur.

Thus, one has at least the cases of $p_1 \rightarrow p_2$ (interaction) and $p \rightarrow -p$ with a 3.14 phase shift. This begs the question of whether one may have an interaction that only introduces a phase shift. This implies no force, but still an interaction, something one does not see in Newtonian mechanics. We consider the well-known Bohm-Aharonov effect as an example of such a situation.